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Structural Change from Agriculture to Industry on Environmental Degradation in Sub-Saharan Africa

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Abstract

The increasing sectorial change on the environment are becoming a serious call for concern in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) especially due to the need for speedy growth. This study evaluate the relationship between structural change from Agriculture to Industry and environmental degradation in sub-Saharan Africa. The study made use of secondary data for 37 SSA countries collected from World Bank Development Indicators. With the help of the Feasible Generalized Least Square (FGLS) technique, the result indicated that industrial value added and its square a U-shaped effect on environmental degradation while agricultural value added and its squared exerts an inverted U-shaped on environmental degradation in SSA. The study also supports the porter's hypothesis in SSA. From the findings, it was recommended that In addition, consistent and forward looking industrialisation and urbanisation policies should be targeted towards investing in clean and affordable energy that induces a positive impact on the environment and Kind attention and high fine should be place on company that pollutes the environment above the stated optimal level.

Keywords: Structural Change, Agricultural Valued Added, Industries Value Added and Environmental Degradation

1. Introduction

The consequences of climate change for both human populations and ecosystems have consistently raised concerns among researchers and sparked public discourse. The greenhouse effect is recognized as the primary driver of global warming, functioning as a natural mechanism that elevates the Earth's surface temperature through the retention of heat in the atmosphere (Alola et al., 2019 & Kweku et al., 2018). Key gases contributing to the greenhouse effect include Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Methane, Fluorinated gases, and Nitrous oxide. An analysis of historical and contemporary global trends reveals that CO₂ emissions increased by 58% from 1990 to 2014, although there was a noted deceleration in the annual growth rate in 2012 (Trends in Global CO₂ emission, 2016). A report from the United States Environmental Protection Agency in 2017 highlighted that carbon dioxide accounted for 82% of total greenhouse gas emissions that year, with methane contributing 10%, Nitrous oxide 6%, and fluorinated gases 3%. Jain and Sarma (2017)

attribute this trend significantly to structural changes and the rise of high-value-added manufacturing and industries, particularly in Asian nations.

In reviewing the literature, it is evident that structural change impacts economic development in two primary ways. The first is the transition from agriculture to industrial production, known as the industrialization process, while the second involves the shift from industrial to service sectors, referred to as the tertiarization process. This framework is grounded in the three-sector analysis proposed by Clark (1957), which posits that as income levels rise, economies evolve from a primary sector focused on agriculture to a secondary sector centred on industry, leading to increased pollution levels. Subsequently, as a nation achieves greater prosperity, the economy transitions to a tertiary sector focused on services, resulting in a reduction of environmental pollution (Alam, 2015; Linden and Mahmood, 2007). The increasing awareness of the impacts of environmental pollution has led to heightened public demand for essential services such as healthcare, education, security, and improved living conditions (Eurostat, 2014). According to a previous study by Alam (2015), the Environmental Kuznet Curve (EKC) hypothesis explores the connection between phases of economic growth – often referred to as the Three-sector analysis – and environmental pollution. While earlier research has been less effective in elucidating the EKC hypothesis (Kander, 2005), the observed decline in global CO₂ emissions from 2012 to 2015 has reignited discussions on the topic.

Structural change analysis highlights the significance of structural shifts as a catalyst for varying growth rates, stemming from transitions between low and high value-added activities. A notable instance is Asia, which has transitioned from low to high value-added sectors since the early 1990s, in contrast to South America and Africa, which have experienced shifts in the opposite direction (Giovanni & Massimiliano, n.d.). McMillan et al. (2017) examine structural transformation and fundamental growth drivers, revealing considerable cross-country variability among emerging nations that have undergone periods of both rapid and sluggish growth. From an integrated structural change and environment (SCE) perspective, it is crucial to investigate how different sectors and regions respond to environmental regulations to better understand the dynamics of economic and environmental performance. Dennis and Işcan (2009) analyse both demand-side effects (Engel) and supply-side effects (productivity, capital deepening), emphasizing that demand effects are particularly significant in long-term contexts, while technological and productivity-related factors may dominate medium-term trends.

From SCE viewpoint, the manufacturing and industrial sectors warrant focused attention. Manufacturing continues to be a primary driver of economic growth, attributed to its significant economic multiplier effects and technological advancements (UNIDO, 2018). However, this sector is also a major contributor to global CO₂ emissions. The rise in innovation across various nations has spurred urbanization and

modernization, which in turn has led to heightened pollution levels, overexploitation of energy resources, and increased industrial activity and energy consumption. Gessese (2006) notes that industrial growth can alleviate environmental pressures linked to poverty. Conversely, the industry also places significant demands on the environment through the extensive use of natural resources and energy, alongside the production of waste and pollution. Many industries from developed nations, seeking to maximize profits and minimize operational costs, often relocate to developing countries. This trend poses risks, as the expansion of industries in these regions, often with minimal regard for pollution control, could jeopardize the health and safety of local populations in the long term. In Africa, human activities further exacerbate environmental pressures, particularly as the continent heavily relies on agriculture for its economic development. Agricultural practices provide employment, income, and food security, yet in numerous African nations, these activities have become exploitative, leading to detrimental changes in local ecosystems, including soil compaction, river silting, erosion, and deforestation.

African countries predominantly depend on livestock, agriculture, and fossil fuels for economic growth, a reliance that has resulted in significant environmental degradation. For instance, Equatorial Guinea emitted over 15 million tonnes of carbon in 2019, accounting for nearly 0.03% of global emissions (Climate Watch, 2022). Chad's emissions exceeded 105 million tonnes, accounting for 0.21% of global pollution. The Central African Republic contributed over 46 million tonnes of emissions, while Cameroon led the CEMAC region with approximately 0.25% of global pollution, totalling more than 124 million tonnes. Gabon emitted over 19 million tonnes, and the Republic of Congo released more than 30 million tonnes of CO₂ (Climate Watch, 2022). This analysis reveals a concerning trend of increasing environmental degradation in sub-Saharan countries, highlighting the urgent need for effective strategies to address this issue. Despite various studies conducted across different economic blocs (Li and Ullah, 2022; Ojekemi et al., 2022; and Sinha et al., 2022), there remains a lack of comprehensive analysis specific to sub-Saharan Africa. This research aims to explore the sectorial impacts on environmental degradation in the region, assisting member countries in achieving their environmental goals as outlined by the United Nations and the Paris Agreement. In many sub-Saharan African nations, non-renewable energy sources predominantly drive the production of goods and services. Furthermore, Pea-Assounga and Wu (2022) noted that CO₂ emissions from coal combustion represent approximately 42% of global emissions. These countries must reduce their dependence on energy sources like coal, invest in renewable energy alternatives, and enhance their environmental policies. Existing research has demonstrated that excessive reliance on non-renewable energy can lead to environmental degradation (Sahoo & Sethi, 2021; Usman & Makhdum, 2021). Consequently, this study seeks to address the following question: Do sectorial shares, represented by agricultural, industrial, and service sector outputs, influence or mitigate

environmental pollution in sub-Saharan countries? Second, does the Pollution Heaven hypothesis applicable in sub-Saharan Countries? Third, what is the quadratic effect of sectorial value added on environmental degradation in Sub-Saharan? The remainder of this study is organized as follows. Section 2, we review recent related literature that discusses the impact of structural transformation on Environmental Degradation. Next, this study will explain methods used in estimating and analysing the effect of structural transformation factors on environmental degradation in Section 3. The empirical findings and discussion are covered in Section 4 of this study and concluded in Section 5.

2. Literature Review

Structural change (SC) primarily pertains to shifts in the employment and value-added structure of the economy, influenced by market dynamics, technological advancements, and consumer demand. The economic composition, including sectorial shares and integration at both national and global levels, is crucial for understanding key aggregate metrics such as labour productivity. This study will concentrate on sectorial shares, utilizing agricultural, industrial, and service value added as indicators of structural change. Environmental degradation is defined as a deterioration in environmental quality, which may result from both human and natural activities. Consequently, carbon dioxide emissions serve as a metric for assessing environmental degradation.

In many instances, researchers investigating the factors contributing to environmental degradation focus on the relationship between economic growth and pollution, as outlined in the Environmental Kuznets Hypothesis. According to Foluso et al. (2022), this hypothesis can be divided into two segments: the "race to the bottom" and the "race to the top." The first segment suggests that increasing income leads to greater environmental degradation (Yandle, 2004). This theory emphasizes the government's role in intentionally lowering environmental standards and regulations to attract foreign investment (Dasgupta et al., 2002; Gray, 2002; Greaker, 2007). Conversely, the second segment argues that rising income correlates with improved environmental quality (Yandle, 2004). 1. Many governments are still in the early stages of development, and in their efforts to attract foreign investors and companies, including those that contribute to pollution, they often compromise environmental standards. However, as these nations achieve greater financial stability and economic growth, they are in a position to implement stricter environmental regulations aimed at reducing emissions. This situation has significant implications for industrial development, particularly in many African countries, where industrial growth frequently occurs without adequate consideration of environmental consequences such as wildlife habitats, resource depletion, air quality, and waste management issues. Economic growth can manifest through various avenues, including investment, trade, and income generation. Smulders

(2000) noted that while economic growth can improve living standards, it also has a negative aspect, as it may exacerbate global greenhouse gas issues over time.

In the context of trade and the environment, two contrasting theoretical frameworks emerge, both reflecting similar dynamics: the Pollution Haven Hypothesis (PHH) and the Porter Hypothesis (PH). The PHH suggests that industries that generate pollution tend to move to regions with less stringent environmental regulations. This concept was initially introduced by Copeland and Taylor (1994), who argued that companies operating in highly regulated countries, such as the United States and Canada, face direct competition from firms in less regulated countries, like Mexico, where environmental standards are more lenient. 1. The authors forecasted that Mexico would face an environmental catastrophe, while the United States would experience a job crisis. They argued that trade liberalization would lead companies producing environmentally harmful goods to relocate from affluent nations with stringent environmental laws to developing countries with more lenient regulations. Consequently, these developing nations would turn into pollution havens for the dirty industries of wealthier countries. The Pollution Haven Hypothesis (PHH) anticipated significant environmental degradation in these developing countries due to their weaker regulatory frameworks (Fozia et al., 2018). In contrast, the Porter Hypothesis presents a counterargument, suggesting that stringent environmental regulations in a company's home country can drive the adoption of cleaner and more efficient technologies, ultimately lowering marginal costs and enhancing firm productivity. This, in turn, would make these firms more competitive.

Table 1: Summary of Related Literature

Author	Year	Country	Methods	Findings
Festus et al. (2020)	1980 - 2014	Sub-Saharan Africa	The Panel Pooled Mean Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (PMG-ARDL)	Agricultural Value added reduces emission in Sub-Saharan Africa while Urbanisation and natural resource Rent increases CO ₂ emission in the Long Run
Haolei Gu and Yan Chen (2020)	2020 -2024	China	Fractional Grey Multivariable Convolution Model	The results show that the secondary industry has the most significant impact on the public's attention to air pollution compared with the primary and tertiary industries.
Duojiao et al., (2022)	2009 - 2018	European Countries		Agricultural emissions, on the other hand, does not significantly affect the three independent variables (but it has a negative effect on cereal and positive impact on vegetable production.
Ali et al., (2023)	1997 - 2020	26 African Countries	The Two-step Generalised Method of Moment	The results show that agricultural production and labour decrease pollution
Jermittiparsert (2021)	1995 - 2015	Association of South East Asian Nations (ASEAN)	Panel regression	Study results confirm that industrialization is a direct cause of environmental sustainability issues as reflected in the high levels of CO ₂ emissions from transport (% of total fuel combustion). At the same time,

				urbanization and human capital index are causing a decline in the levels of carbon emission.
Alhassan and Ibrahim (2022)	1970 - 2017	Ghana	Fully Modified Least Square Technique (FMOLS)	Industrialisation has a negative Significant effect on Ecological Footprint while education and financial development improves environmental sustainability.
Jain and Sama (2017)	1990 - 2015	Selected Asian Countries	Panel Regression	Findings suggest that the industrialization process will induce increased environmental pollution, while the tertiarization process lowers environmental pollution. Further, the results support the existence of an inverted-U curve between affluence level and CO ₂ emissions
Abdallh and Abugamos (2017)	1980 - 2014	MENA countries	Semi-parametric Panel Fixed effect regression	The findings reveal evidence to support an inverted U-shaped relationship between Urbanisation and Carbon emission
Bing Ye and Qianwen (2022)	2009 - 2017	China	Difference to Difference Method of Panel Regression	The results suggest that environmental regulation reduces the fixed asset investment and value-added of tertiary sectors but increases the establishment of legal entities in tertiary sectors.

Wenxuan (2023)	2006 - 2021	China	GMM	Findings shows there is a negative correlation between higher education and environmental pollution in China, it is not significant. From different regions, the coefficients in the eastern are positive which means aggravated environmental pollution, and the coefficients in the central region are not significant, but higher education in the western region improves environmental pollution.
Rosenblum (2000)		USA	Economic Input-Output Life Cycle Assessment Model	Findings indicates that several environmental metrics (e.g., hazardous waste generation), service industries have significant indirect environmental effects on an economy-wide basis even when their direct emissions are negligible.
Jain and Sarma (2017)	1990 - 2015	Asian Countries	Panel Regression	Findings suggest that the industrialization process will induce increased environmental pollution, while the tertiarization process lowers environmental pollution.

An examination of the existing literature reveals that research has been conducted in Africa regarding the relationship between agriculture, industry, natural resource rents, and environmental quality as measured by CO₂ emissions. This study introduces the concept of a quadratic effect—specifically, the squares of agriculture and industry—on environmental degradation to determine whether this relationship exhibits an inverted U-shape. Furthermore, the research utilizes advanced estimation techniques to address issues such as cross-sectional dependence, heteroscedasticity, and autocorrelation, which are prevalent in panel analyses, in contrast to traditional panel regression methods.

3. Data and Methodology

This research utilized panel data from 37 sub-Saharan African countries spanning the years 1995 to 2022. The dependent variable analysed was carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, while the independent variables included agricultural value added and its square, industrial value added and its square, and tertiary value added and its square to assess structural changes. The inclusion of squared terms aims to capture the quadratic effect. Additional independent variables comprised urbanization, trade openness, and gross domestic product per capita. Data for these variables were sourced from the World Bank Development Indicators for the selected 37 sub-Saharan African nations, with other countries excluded due to data unavailability. A detailed description of the variables is provided in Table 1.

Estimation Process

The research commenced with the calculation of summary statistics for all relevant variables to examine their distinct characteristics. Utilizing panel data from 37 Sub-Saharan countries, the study first conducted a test for cross-sectional dependence prior to model estimation, as this determines the approach based on the presence or absence of such dependence. Given the substantial number of cross-sectional units, the Pesaran (2004) CD Test was employed to assess cross-sectional dependence. In cases where cross-sectional dependence was identified, the first-generation panel unit tests, which assume cross-sectional independence, such as those proposed by Maddala et al. (1999), Levin et al. (2002), and Choi (2001), were deemed inappropriate for this analysis. Instead, the study utilized the Pesaran (2007) panel unit root test for all variables, with the exception of industry value added and its squared term, for which the Im et al. (2003) test was applied due to insignificant cross-sectional dependence values. Issues such as cross-sectional dependence, heteroscedasticity, and correlation pose significant challenges in the error term of panel regression. As noted by Bai et al. (2020), two approaches can address these issues: employing an Ordinary Least Squares estimator with robust standard errors to account for heteroscedasticity and correlation (Vogelsang, 2012) or utilizing the Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) method. This study opted for the

FGLS approach, which accommodates heteroscedasticity, cross-sectional dependence, and correlation, in contrast to the former method, as its clustered standard errors yield more conservative confidence intervals. Hansen (2007) highlighted that FGLS effectively addresses serial correlation and clustering issues in fixed effect panel and multi-level models.

Model Estimation

This study explores the relationship between structural change and environmental degradation in Africa by utilizing the IPAT model and assessing the validity of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) within the CEMAC Zone. The IPAT framework, introduced by Ehrlich and Holdren in 1971, illustrates how human activities contribute to environmental impact. The model examines the effects of three key factors: population growth (P), per capita affluence measured by economic output (A), and technological advancements per unit of consumption and production (T), which collectively influence environmental impact (I):

$I = P.A.T$(1) To address the limitations of the original IPAT model, such as constraints on the permissible ranges of the variables, Dietz and Rosa (1997) proposed the STIRPAT framework for analysing environmental outcomes.

$$I = \alpha + P^{b_{it}} A^{c_{it}} T^{d_{it}} \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where α , b , c , and d are parameters of the model and ε is the error term and the subscript $i.t$ indicates countries and time in panel data. The elasticities imply non linearity which can be linearized as shown in equation (2)

$$\ln I = \alpha + b \ln P_{it} + c \ln A_{it} + d \ln T_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Thus, our model for this study will be express as:

$$CO_{2it} = \alpha_i + \gamma_{1i} UB_{it} + \gamma_{2i} GDP_{it} + \gamma_{3i} INDUS_{it} + \gamma_{4i} \phi_{it} + v_{it} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Equation 3 illustrates that environmental impact (I) is represented by CO2 emissions, while UB denotes urban population, serving as an indicator of urbanization (P). GDP reflects output growth, acting as a measure of affluence (A), and INDUS signifies industrial value added, representing technology (T). Additionally, other control variables are included. We incorporated the composition effect, which considers value added in agriculture and services, to account for structural changes, along with their squared terms to assess their quadratic effects. Based on the Pollution Haven Hypothesis (PHH), it is posited that developing countries may become pollution havens for the more polluting industries from advanced nations; therefore, trade openness was added as a

variable affecting environmental degradation. Consequently, the models we estimated for this study are articulated as follows:

$$\ln\text{CO}_{2it} = \delta_i + \delta_{1i}\ln\text{GDP}_{it} + \delta_{2i}\text{AGR}_{it} + \delta_{3i}\text{INDUS}_{it} + \delta_{4i}\text{INDUS}_{it}^2 + \delta_{5i}\text{SER}_{it} + \mu_{it}.$$

$$\ln\text{CO}_{2it} = \beta_i + \beta_{1i}\text{UB}_{it} + \beta_{2i}\ln\text{GDP}_{it} + \beta_{3i}\text{AGR}_{it} + \beta_{4i}\text{AGR}_{it}^2 + \beta_{5i}\text{FDI}_{it} + \beta_{6i}\text{INDUS}_{it} + V_{it}.$$

Table 2: Indicators, Unit of Measurement and their Sources

Indicators	Unit Measure	source
Urban Population a proxy for Urbanisation (UB)	% of Total Population	WDI
Carbon dioxide emission	kt	WDI
Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing Value added (AGR)	% of GDP	WDI
Industry (including Construction), Value added (INDUS)	% of GDP	WDI
Service Value Added (SER)	% of GDP	WDI
Real GDP	Constant 2015 US\$	WDI
Foreign Direct Investment net inflow. (FDI)	% of GDP	WDI
Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing Value added (AGR) Squared (ARG ²)	Square of AGR	
Industry (including Construction), Value added squared (INDUS ²)	Square of INDUS	

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Preliminary results

The preliminary results involve the descriptive statistics of each of the variables under study namely, Carbon dioxide emission (CO₂), Real Gross Domestic product (GDP), Agricultural Value added (AGR) and its Squared (AGR²), Industry value added (INDUS) and its squared (INDUS²), Service Value Added (SER), Urbanisation (UB), and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
lnCO ₂	1,036	7.885789	1.593038	4.356709	13.0601
lnGDP	1,036	22.95621	1.414231	20.07301	27.00617
AGR	1,036	21.49184	13.48059	1.738935	61.41626
AGR ²	1,036	643.4502	694.2434	3.023895	3771.957
INDUS	1,036	25.40541	11.8299	4.428779	72.71737

INDUS2	1,036	785.2463	812.7313	19.61408	5287.816
SER	1,036	46.50101	11.30579	12.43525	93.36183
UB	1,036	39.04094	16.66548	7.211	90.735
FDI	1,036	3.524335	5.670989	-18.91777	56.26385

Source: Author (2023)

The mean of the squared industry value added in sub-Saharan Africa stands at 785.246, marking it as the highest among all examined variables. This is followed by the squared agricultural value added, which has a mean of 643.450, and service value added at 46.501. The urban population, serving as a proxy for urbanization, has a mean of 39.0409, while the variable with the lowest mean is the net inflow of foreign direct investment as a percentage of GDP. Notably, the squared industrial value added and the squared agricultural value added exhibit the highest maximum values, whereas carbon dioxide emissions record the lowest maximum value across the 37 sub-Saharan countries. The variable with the lowest minimum value is the net inflow of foreign direct investment (-18.917), while real gross domestic product has the highest minimum value at 20.073. In analysing panel data, we assess cross-sectional dependence using the Pesaran (2004) CD test, followed by the Pesaran (2007) panel unit root test, which accounts for cross-sectional dependence, as detailed in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4: Test for Cross Sectional Dependence

Variable	CD-test	p-value	average joint T	mean ρ	mean abs(ρ)
CO2	+ 99.706	0.000	28.00	+ 0.73	0.80
AGR	+ 38.497	0.000	28.00	+ 0.28	0.44
INDUS	+ .243	0.808	28.00	+ 0.00	0.40
SER	+ 6.495	0.000	28.00	+ 0.05	0.40
AGR2	+ 39.753	0.000	28.00	+ 0.29	0.44
INDUS2	+ .249	0.804	28.00	+ 0.00	0.39
UB	+ 105.707	0.000	28.00	+ 0.77	0.92
FDI	+ 15.159	0.000	28.00	+ 0.11	0.24
GDP	+ 123.546	0.000	28.00	+ 0.90	0.90

With the null hypothesis of sectional independence, the test indicated that there is cross sectional dependence indicating that data are correlated across groups. Since industry value added and its squared are having a probability value that is greater than 0.05, the first generational unit root test of Im st al. (2003) is employed to test for their unit root.

Table 5: Panel Unit Root Test

Variables	Critical Value	10%	5%	1%	Integration
CO2	-2.303	-2.04	-2.11	-2.23	I(0)
AGR	-2.453	-2.04	-2.11	-2.23	I(0)
AGR2	-2.538	-2.04	-2.11	-2.23	I(0)
SER	-2.187	-2.04	-2.11	-2.23	I(0)

FDI	-3.435	-2.04	-2.11	-2.23	I(0)
INDUS	-2.5402	-1.690	-1.73	-1.820	I(0)
INDUS2	2.4489	-1.690	-1.73	-1.820	I(0)
LogGDP	-2.252	-2.54	-2.61	-2.73	I(0)
UB	-2.852	-2.54	-2.61	-2.73	I(0)

The stationarity test is a prerequisite for panel data analysis to determine the order in which the variables gain stationarity. From the Panel unit root test (constant and trend) for all the variables in Table 5, we observed that the variables are stationary at level.

The Feasible Generalised Least Square estimation for cross sectional and serial correlation require us to estimate the fixed effect an test for heteroscedasticity which might be due to slopes, and or varying standard error across cross section. The results with that of the feasible generalised least square for model 1 is presented on Table 6.

Table 6: Regression Result for the First Model

VARIABLES	(FE) ICO2	(RE) ICO2	(FGLS) ICO2
AGR	0.00370* (0.00196)	-0.00903 (0.00912)	-0.0170*** (0.000226)
INDUS	-0.00527 (0.00347)	0.0129 (0.0630)	-0.00684*** (0.000469)
SER	0.00168 (0.00139)	-0.00450 (0.00626)	0.0140*** (0.000254)
INDUS ²	0.000117** (.0000481)	-0.000502 (0.00189)	0.000224*** (.0000068)
logGDP	1.040*** (0.0196)	0.969*** (0.0831)	1.012*** (0.000944)
Constant	-16.11*** (0.487)	-13.86*** (2.264)	-15.63*** (0.0305)
Prob. F Value	0.000		
Observations	1,036	1,036	1,036
R-squared	0.784		
Number of C_id	37	37	37

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

The results from the fixed effect regression presented in Table 6 reveal that agricultural value added (AGR), the square of industrial value added (INDUS²), service value added (SER), and real GDP positively impact environmental degradation in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Conversely, industrial value added (INDUS) has a negative effect on environmental degradation. It is noteworthy that INDUS and SER do not show significant effects, while the other variables do. The adjusted R-squared value indicates

that approximately 78 percent of the variation in environmental degradation can be attributed to AGR, INDUS, SER, and the logarithm of real GDP. It is essential to note that despite employing a fixed model to address cross-sectional heteroscedasticity by incorporating cross-sectional identity, the model still exhibits heteroscedasticity, as indicated by its probability F-value.

The existence of heteroscedasticity necessitated the use of random effect regression, as shown in Table 6 above. The findings indicate that AGR, SER, and INDUS2 have a negative but insignificant effect on environmental degradation in SSA, with only the impact of GDP being statistically significant. The feasible generalized least squares results suggest that, on average, an increase in AGR leads to a reduction in environmental degradation in Sub-Saharan Africa. Additionally, lower levels of industrial value added (INDUS) significantly negatively affect environmental degradation, while higher levels of industrial value added (INDUS2) demonstrate a positive and significant effect on environmental degradation in SSA. Industrial growth places constraints on the environment through its various impacts. 1. The expansion of industrial activities places significant pressure on the environment due to the heavy consumption of natural resources and energy, leading to increased waste and pollution. Consequently, the value added by industry demonstrates a U-shaped relationship with environmental degradation in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). In contrast, the value added from the services sector has a notably positive impact on environmental degradation. Additionally, the logarithm of real GDP indicates a significant positive correlation with environmental degradation. This suggests that as countries in SSA prioritize economic growth, they inadvertently contribute to environmental deterioration. This observation aligns with the initial phase of the environmental Kuznets curve hypothesis, as articulated by Yandle (2004), which posits that a nation's rising income tends to accelerate environmental decline.

Table 7: Regression Result for the Second Model

VARIABLES	(FE)	(RE)	(FGLS)
	lnCO2	lnCO2	lnCO2
UB	0.00677*** (0.00251)	0.0165 (0.0212)	0.00729*** (0.00005)
lnGDP	0.977*** (0.0302)	0.703*** (0.129)	1.005*** (0.00113)
AGR	0.0137*** (0.00493)	0.0373 (0.0600)	-0.0473*** (0.000293)
AGR ²	-0.000158** (.000070)	-0.00553 (0.00924)	0.000504*** (.0000045)
FDI	0.00443*** (0.00130)	-0.00240 (0.00657)	-0.00129*** (0.000160)
INDUS	0.00230* (0.00135)	-0.000381 (0.00552)	-0.00444*** (0.000149)
Constant	-15.07*** (0.644)	-9.237*** (2.757)	-14.65*** (0.0219)
Prob. F Value	0.000		
Observations	1,036	1,036	1,036
R-squared	0.788		
Number of C_id	37	37	37

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

The feasible generalized least squares (FGLS) method is preferred over both fixed and random effects models when addressing cross-sectional dependence and heteroscedasticity; therefore, our analysis will concentrate on the FGLS outcomes. The primary aim of this model was to evaluate the pollution haven hypothesis in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). To investigate this hypothesis, the study utilized foreign direct investment (FDI) data, revealing a significant negative impact of FDI on environmental degradation in SSA. These findings contradict the hypothesis, suggesting that while SSA countries actively promote FDI, they have implemented specific regulations to govern investments from developed nations. Our results align with Porter's hypothesis, which posits that stringent environmental regulations in a home country lead to the adoption of cleaner and more efficient technologies, ultimately lowering marginal costs and enhancing firm productivity. The variable representing agricultural value added indicates that at lower levels, it contributes to increased CO₂ emissions, while intensified agricultural activities lead to a reduction in environmental degradation. This suggests that small-scale agricultural practices, which add minimal value, exert greater pressure on the environment due to their rudimentary methods. In contrast, large-scale agricultural operations prioritize environmental quality. Consequently, agricultural growth in SSA is

essential not only for economic development but also for maintaining environmental integrity. This finding corroborates the work of Ali et al. (2023), who assert that agricultural production mitigates pollution, demonstrating an inverted U-shaped relationship with environmental degradation. 1. The variable INDUS, in conjunction with AGR and AGR2, has a notable negative impact on environmental degradation in Sub-Saharan African (SSA) nations. This observation aligns with Gessese's (2006) assertion that industrial development alleviates environmental pressures linked to poverty. The FGLS results presented in Table 7 further demonstrate that the level of Urbanization (UB) has a significant positive effect on environmental degradation in SSA. As urban populations increase, so does the consumption of energy resources, leading to higher carbon dioxide emissions. This positive correlation between Urbanization and environmental degradation is consistent with the findings of Festus et al. (2020), yet it contrasts with Sharma's (2011) research, which identified a negative relationship between urbanization and carbon dioxide emissions.

5. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

This study investigates the transition from agriculture to industry and its effects on environmental degradation in SSA. Utilizing secondary data from the World Development Indicators for 37 Sub-Saharan countries, the Pesaran (2007) unit root test for panel data with cross-sectional dependence was applied. The Feasible Generalized Least Squares method reveals that agricultural value added and its squared term exhibit an inverted U-shaped relationship with environmental degradation, while industrial value added and its squared term demonstrate a U-shaped effect. Our findings do not support the Pollution Haven Hypothesis.

It is advisable for SSA countries to implement robust policies that critically assess the technologies utilized within their borders to mitigate the adverse effects associated with these technologies. Furthermore, there should be a focus on developing consistent and forward-thinking industrialization and urbanization strategies aimed at investing in clean and affordable energy solutions that positively impact the environment. Many policymakers in SSA prioritize attracting both domestic and international investors to foster the development of their nations and to draw investments into cleaner, technology-driven, and environmentally sustainable industries. Strict attention and significant penalties should be imposed on companies that exceed permissible pollution levels.

Agricultural development is crucial for the growth of SSA nations; however, certain agricultural practices, such as bush fallowing, contribute to environmental degradation, compounded by the use of primitive farming tools. Additionally, the rise of agro-industries in the region has led to increased carbon dioxide emissions. The path forward for SSA countries involves the adoption of long-term technologies that minimize carbon

emissions while accommodating the growth of agro-processing industries. Furthermore, the governments of these nations should contemplate implementing subsidies for agro-industries that utilize low-carbon technologies to enhance the demand for such innovations. Another important policy consideration is that while urbanization can alleviate poverty, it may also lead to increased pollution levels. Therefore, it is essential for Sub-Saharan African countries to engage in strategic urban planning, complemented by effective transportation and waste management systems. Additionally, these countries have the opportunity to allocate funds from economic growth to tackle environmental degradation issues. This approach would significantly enhance environmental quality, thereby improving the overall well-being of the local population.

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